

Artificial Intelligence in Endodontics (Part II)

Dr. Rajiv K. Chugh

President Elect, Indian Dental Association (H.O.)

Member, Dental Council of India

Secretary General, Indian Academy of Restorative Dentistry

Editor-in-Chief (Asia), UPDENT- A Journal of Advanced Dentistry

Senate Member, Pierre Fauchard Academy, India Section

10.4880/zenodo.5296250

Artificial Intelligence developments hint at potential advantages for health care, including fewer postoperative complications, higher quality of life, better decision-making, and far fewer needless procedures.

In endodontics, artificial intelligence(AI) is gaining more relevance. Its significance in endodontic treatment planning and disease diagnosis is growing at the moment. The advent of AI has influenced the imaging and pathology, dental image diagnostics, caries detection and robotic assistance. A few of its applications in endodontics are mentioned and described in detail below:

Detection

AI in endodontics has been for detection of periapical lesions, root fractures, determining the working length and to visualize the tooth morphology.

Periapical Lesions Detection

It might be difficult for clinicians to determine a diagnosis and a plan of treatment for teeth showing periapical lesions and/or their symptoms. Approximately 75% of instances with radiolucent jaw lesions are caused by the prevalent condition - apical periodontitis. Early detection may increase the efficacy of treatment, preventing it from spreading to other tissues and reducing potential problems. IOPA and OPG are the two 2-dimensional diagnostic methods that are most frequently employed in everyday clinical practice to detect apical periodontitis . Periapical lesions are often seen as radiolucencies on radiographs. However, because the actual 3-D anatomy is condensed into a 2-D image, the information gleaned from these periapical radiographs is unreliable. CBCT imaging was developed as a 3D imaging technique to precisely detect periapical lesions and assess their location and size. It has been found that when diagnosing apical periodontitis in teeth with filled roots, CBCT imaging had less accuracy. The characteristics of periapical radiolucency and alveolar bone resorption can both aid in the creation of Artificial Intelligence models for the detection of periapical

pathology and periodontitis. AI can assist in identifying alveolar bone loss and second for quantifying the extent of the bone loss. It also helps to categorize the severity of periapical lesions with regard to the diagnosis of periapical pathology. It is a great adjunct to separate granuloma from periapical cysts using CBCT images; it is valued highly in clinical practice because it allows periapical granulomas to recover following root canal therapy without the need for surgery.

Root Fractures Detection

Vertical root fractures (VRF) are a common occurrence and constitute 2% to 5% of crown/root fractures. The incidence has increased significantly since the start of the pandemic. Teeth grinding and teeth clenching related to the increased stress levels has spiked. It is very much important to detect these root fractures at an initial stage in order to prevent damage to its supporting structures. Cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) imaging and radiographs assist in identifying a Vertical Root Fracture which perhaps is challenging to diagnose. The absence of a conclusive diagnosis might lead to needless surgery or tooth extraction. AI is a useful tool for identifying VRFs on panoramic radiographs. In comparison to pictures from 2-D radiographs, they found that fracture identification of roots on CBCT images is superior in relation to specificity, accuracy, and sensitivity.

Morphology of Root and Root Canal System

It is very important to identify the different types of root and root canal systems in the effectiveness of nonsurgical root canal therapy. Understanding the morphology of the root canal system is a crucial adjunct in the treatment planning. Cone-beam computed tomography imaging and periapical radiography have often been employed for this purpose. When compared to radiography, Cone beam computed tomography imaging has shown to be more accurate in determining the root and root canal geometries. However, it cannot be advised in standard clinical practice due to the exposure to radiations.

Determination of Working Length

Correct determination of the Working Length is critical for successful root canal treatment outcomes. Various methods are used to assess working length are radiography, digital tactile sense, electronic apex locators, the reaction of the patient to a paper point or file point placed into the root canal system, and CBCT imaging. Radiography and electronic apex locators are the most frequently employed techniques among the clinicians. The clarity of the image in digital radiography is essential for the accurate interpretation of the anatomy of the root canal system. The radiographic interpretations sometimes found to be misleading resulting in misdiagnosis. There is a need to use computer-based techniques to provide consistently precise working lengths. AI has been found effective to locate the radiographic apical foramen and determine minor anatomic constriction.

Retreatment Predictions

AI has been utilized to predict the result outcomes of nonsurgical retreatment of the root canal with risks and benefits. One of the system's strongest aspects is its ability to correctly forecast how the retreatment would turn out. To increase the accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity, future research is on its way.

Prediction of the Viability of Stem Cells

The stem cells extraction from the tooth pulp in many regenerative treatments has been assessed. By assessing the stem cells' survival utilizing AI, it was possible to predict the result outcomes. To predict cell survival after a variety of regeneration procedures that are subject to microbial infection, AI was found to be an effective tool.

To be concluded in the next part.....

